

SOCIAL SCIENCES

GENDER PROJECTS AS A FACTOR IN PROMOTING GENDER EQUALITY IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article examines the key areas and results of national and international projects in Ukraine aimed at achieving gender equality. Particular attention is paid to the initiatives of Ukrainian organizations working to form a gender-sensitive society through educational activities and overcoming stereotypes. Effective practices implemented within the framework of such projects as the platform “Women are 50% of Ukraine’s success”, the activities of the Institute of Mass Information, public organizations “Business Development Center” and “Youth for Human Rights” are analyzed. It is determined that the integration of international experience, active public participation and the development of institutional mechanisms contribute to the strengthening of gender policy. The need for further improvement of mechanisms for implementing gender projects is emphasized, in particular in terms of monitoring, financing and adaptation to the Ukrainian context. The results of the study can become the basis for the formation of an effective toolkit for implementing gender equality at the regional and institutional levels.

Keywords: gender equality, gender policy, gender projects, gender stereotypes, inclusive society, social equity.

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Relevance. Ensuring gender equality is a relevant strategic goal of today, both at the level of the global economy as a whole and at the national level in particular. Overcoming gender disparities not only contributes to social equity, stimulates economic development, expands opportunities for individuals and Ukrainian society, but also serves as a priority in the context of Ukraine's integration into the EU, where gender standards are an integral part of social policy. The implementation of national and international projects on gender issues plays a significant role in the transformation of Ukrainian society, the formation of inclusive policies and increasing the level of social equity. The analysis of such projects allows us to assess the effectiveness of implemented initiatives, identify best practices and adapt them to specific regional or institutional needs. At the same time, international projects become an important source of knowledge and resources for improving national approaches to addressing gender issues; their analysis not only expands the scientific understanding of the effectiveness of various approaches to gender policy, but also provides practical tools for implementing changes in society.

At the same time, regional adaptation of complex gender indices and indicators remains a challenge. This requires a systematic analysis of projects implemented

at different levels to determine their relevance and usefulness in specific conditions. Consideration of national initiatives in combination with international experience allows us to identify synergies between local and global approaches to solving gender problems. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to study the main directions and results of national and international projects in Ukraine on gender issues, assess their effectiveness and opportunities for adaptation to the regional and institutional levels. Such analysis will contribute to the development of tools for the further implementation of complex gender indices in practice and ensuring greater effectiveness of gender policy.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Research on gender equality is multidimensional and covers social, economic, political and legal aspects. Amartya Sen in his work “Development as Freedom” [6] considers the issue of gender equality in the context of the concept of human development. Nussbaum Martha C. in her work “Women and Human Development: The Capabilities Approach” [14] develops the capability approach theory pioneered by Amartya Sen, complementing it with social and cultural factors that influence women's capabilities. Mieke Verloo in the work “Varieties of Gender Equality: Stretching the Agenda” [13] analyzes approaches to gender equality in various political and social contexts and considers the implementation of international gender initiatives. Grimshaw Damian & Rubery Jill in their study “The Adjusted Gender Pay Gap: a Critical Appraisal of Standard Decomposition Techniques” [9] analyze the main factors influencing gender inequality in employment, as well as the effectiveness of policies aimed at overcoming

this phenomenon. Ukrainian research by Kateryna Levchenko and Tamara Martsenyuk is devoted to gender initiatives in the fields of education, medicine and the labor market, noting both positive trends and the presence of structural barriers. Levchenko K. in her monograph "Gender policy in Ukraine: definition, formation, management" [11] analyzes the current state of gender equality in Ukraine and assesses the effectiveness of state and international initiatives aimed at achieving it. The work of T. Martsenyuk, "Women in Ukrainian Politics: Challenges and Prospects for Change" [12] is a thorough study of the role of women in the political life of Ukraine, which analyzes the dynamics of gender equality in the political sphere, the main barriers to women's participation in elected bodies of government, and opportunities for improving their representation. The authors of the article in previous publications also considered various aspects of gender issues: theoretical and applied foundations of gender research [5]; gender projects in Ukraine, initiated by state structures, state and public organizations, foreign partners (in the form of grants from state structures of Europe, the USA, Canada and other countries, foundations, civil society organizations) [4; 8]; possibilities of adapting Gender Development Index [2], Global Gender Gap Index [3] and Gender Inequality Index [1] to the regional level.

Thus, even a brief review of the literature indicates significant scientific interest in gender equality issues and the need for further analysis of the impact of gender initiatives on the implementation of gender equality in Ukraine.

Presentation of the main material of the study.

Many national and international gender projects aimed at achieving equality between men and women in various spheres have been implemented in Ukraine. Analysis of their areas of activity and organizational features made it possible to classify these projects into the following six main groups: 1) national gender projects; 2) international gender projects of official institutions; 3) gender projects of European organizations and institutions; 4) gender projects of Ukrainian organizations and institutions; 5) gender educational projects of Ukrainian and international organizations and institutions; 6) research into international experience of best practices used in international gender projects.

All of the above types of gender projects were analyzed and detailed in the monograph "Gender Dimensions of Ukraine: Adaptation of Gender Indices to the Subnational Level" [4, pp. 45–172], therefore, in this publication we consider it appropriate to focus specifically on gender projects of Ukrainian organizations and institutions aimed at gender education and changing stereotypes. Ukrainian organizations and institutions are actively implementing projects aimed at raising public awareness of gender issues, changing public perceptions of the roles of women and men, and building a culture of equality. Such initiatives reach a wide target audience, including youth, educators, employers, civil servants, and the general public. The main goals of such projects are: a) forming a public consciousness that supports the principles of gender equality; b) overcoming traditional stereotypes about the roles of men and

women in the family, at work and in society; c) expanding access to knowledge on gender issues through educational programs, trainings and information campaigns; d) creating a gender-sensitive educational environment and media space. Let us give examples of individual effective projects in this area.

The platform "Women are 50% of Ukraine's success" [15] is a social project aimed at activating and supporting women in public and political life, balancing the representation of women and men in key positions in order to accelerate the creation of a truly European model of society. On the platform's website, you can find a selection of 12 projects - online courses for self-education on the topic of gender equality: "Women and Men: Gender for All" (the goal of the course is to help educators and all interested parties understand gender issues; learn to professionally analyze events and social phenomena from a gender perspective, avoid discrimination, better understand their rights and ways to protect them, actively and effectively use the acquired knowledge in public discussions and everyday life), "Implementation of the principles of gender equality in the provision of administrative and social services" (the online course is recommended for representatives of government bodies and local governments, specialists/staff in the field of providing social and administrative services, members/staff of public organizations and all those interested in this topic) and others.

Institute of Mass Information (IMI) [10] is a Ukrainian media public organization that defends the rights of journalists, analyzes the media sphere, covers media-related events, counteracts propaganda and disinformation, and provides media with protective equipment for trips to the combat zone during the Russian-Ukrainian war since 2014. It has representatives in 20 regions of Ukraine and a network of hubs called "Mediabase". The Institute of Mass Information participates in the development of draft laws and media reforms, as well as orders and other documents that regulate the activities of the media and the information space in Ukraine; promotes the investigation of crimes against journalists; actively works in working groups with law enforcement officers. Since 2013, IMI has been systematically monitoring the observance of gender balance by Ukrainian national online media. It records the representation of women experts in key topics, the presence of women as heroines, stereotypes, sexism, discriminatory vocabulary, ageism. Among the most famous IMI projects are "Gender Equality After 134 Years. How Ukrainian Online Media Affirm Sexism in the Media Space", "Gender Imbalance in Propaganda Media. Monitoring Study", "Housewife, Nurse, Sorrowful Mother and Sexy Kitty: One Third of Media Continues to Use Stereotypes and Sexism" and others [7]. IMI was the first to conduct gender monitoring in Ukraine, the goal of which is to show the media mistakes in achieving gender balance, which will contribute to improving the visibility and representation of Ukrainian women.

The public organization "Business Development Center" implemented the project "Gender-Sensitive Business" during 2019–2020. The project is aimed at integrating the principles of gender equality into the

corporate culture of enterprises. The main activities of the project were conducting seminars and consultations for company managers, developing gender-sensitive policies for business, and implementing mechanisms for equal pay for women and men.

The project "Gender Stereotypes and Youth" of the public organization "Youth for Human Rights" (2018-2021) aimed to overcome widespread gender stereotypes among young people and to promote the formation of a new culture of gender equality. The project implemented educational, informational and awareness-raising activities that included both direct work with young people and involvement of the general public through modern communication platforms. The main goals of the project were to raise youth awareness of gender equality and related rights, to debunk gender stereotypes that limit the opportunities of young women and men, to encourage youth to actively participate in solving social and gender problems, and to popularize the ideas of equal opportunities for everyone in society, regardless of gender. During the project implementation, educational classes were held (interactive lessons, seminars and trainings in schools and higher education institutions), information campaigns (on social networks using videos, infographics and posters, launching flash mobs and challenges with hashtags that drew attention to the problems of gender stereotypes, involving youth leaders and bloggers in disseminating information about the project), media products were used (short videos demonstrating the harmful effects of gender stereotypes, thematic booklets and posters for youth centers, schools and public organizations), competitions and public events were held.

The implementation of these and similar projects resulted in the following achievements: a) expanding access to knowledge on gender issues among youth, educators, and the general public; reducing the number of gender stereotypes in the media, educational programs, and corporate culture; c) creating new educational materials that meet the principles of gender equality; d) forming gender-sensitive communities through educational campaigns.

Overall, gender projects aimed at educating and changing stereotypes play a key role in transforming public consciousness in Ukraine. Thanks to these initiatives, public awareness of gender issues is increasing, which contributes to the creation of an inclusive society where equal opportunities are provided for women and men in all spheres of life.

Conclusions. The synergy effect that arises from combining project efforts allows for achieving larger and more sustainable results. Interaction between global and regional initiatives contributes to the exchange of best practices, harmonization of standards and increased institutional capacity. In particular, joint actions ensure more efficient use of resources, elimination of duplication of efforts and alignment of strategic goals across regions. The analysis of the projects showed their comprehensive approach, which includes awareness-raising campaigns, creation of new institutional mechanisms, integration of gender aspects into policies and programs, as well as active participation of civil society. As a result, the following results were achieved:

- increased public awareness of women's rights and gender equality;
- specialized institutions have been created to support victims of violence;
- interaction between government agencies, public organizations, and international partners has been strengthened.

Importantly, many of these initiatives were long-term in nature and had a sustainable impact, creating conditions for further positive change. At the same time, the analysis revealed the need for further improvement of project implementation mechanisms, especially in terms of monitoring effectiveness, securing funding, and adapting international experience to Ukrainian realities.

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